

Newtonian Mechanics from Conservation?

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Newtonian mechanics (including the differential equation called the second law) were developed by Isaac Newton. Later, Lagrange introduced a calculus of variation approach, which when applied to $\int L dt$ (called the action) with L usually $=T-V$, where T =kinetic energy and V , potential, reproduced Newton's second law. The Lagrangian approach is very useful for calculations, but it seems its interpretation of testing different possible paths from the actual one of nature has taken on a kind of physical reality, especially when generalized to path integrals.

Here, we argue that one may equally well obtain Newton's second law from an a priori conservation law. This equation is local, unlike the global Lagrangian approach, suggesting that there are other ways of obtaining the second law than through the extremization of an action, i.e. the testing of various paths.

The a priori conservation law may be obtained by examining a bound state problem with velocity $= dx/dt = 0$ at the end points and time reversal. One may argue for a description of such a problem in terms of an even function of $v(x)$ so that $-v(x)$ and $v(x)$ are treated in the same manner. The simplest form is $v(x) v(x)$ (or $v \cdot v$), but the simplest form is not necessarily the correct one. We try to argue that $v(x) v(x)$ is in fact what one needs and that it must be multiplied by m_0 (rest mass) in the nonrelativistic case. Then, one may find the highest $v(x)v(x)$ value in the bound trajectory and a priori write: $m v(x) v(x) + V_1(x) = E$, where E_1 is some constant and $V_1(x)$, some x function. One may take the derivative of this equation and see it is convenient to insert a $.5$ factor for mvv . The derivative then leads to a differential equation, but one that is obtained locally without any notion of different paths being considered.

We do not suggest that there is any issue with the Lagrangian approach (which is extremely useful for calculations). We only wish to point out that one does not need to rely on the notion of considering different paths with the same endpoints in order to obtain Newton's second law. In other words, there is not necessarily anything inherently physical about different path paths which vary slightly from the correct one.

Newton's Equations and the Lagrangian Approach

Newton stated that a particle in motion or at rest remains in this state unless acted on by a force. His second law is:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \quad \text{where } p = mv \text{ in the nonrelativistic case ((1))}$$

He also introduced the idea of action-reaction and conservation of momentum. The energy conservation law:

$$.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((2)) \text{ where } F = -dV/dx \text{ also emerges from Newtonian mechanics.}$$

Later, Lagrange developed a calculus of variations approach to obtaining Newton's second law which is extremely useful in calculations. He proposed a function called the Lagrangian:

$L = T - V$ (usually) where $T = \text{kinetic energy} = \frac{1}{2} m \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v}$ and $V(x)$ is potential energy ((3))

Next, he suggested that the functional variation an integral called an action:

$$\text{Action} = \int L(x, v, t) dt \quad ((4))$$

yields Newton's second law. If there are constraints, they may be added to ((4)). One may functionally vary ((4)) to obtain Newton's second law.

The point we wish to make is that a variational calculus approach considers different paths with the same endpoints in order to find the one correct path which extremizes ((4)). Even though this is a mathematical approach, it seems there might be a tendency to think that nature somehow calculates ((4)), a global quantity, for various paths and then chooses the correct path, but the differential equation (Newton's second law is in fact a local equation). This tendency of possibly considering nature as testing different paths seems to be carried over into path integral formalism.

We wish to show here that one may obtain Newton's second law from an a priori conservation law which is strictly local. Taking the d/dx derivative of this local equation leads to the local differential equation (i.e. Newton's second law). Thus, we argue that there is a strictly local viewpoint to obtaining Newton's second law which bypasses the need to consider different paths in spacetime with the same endpoint.

A Priori Conservation Law

Consider the case of a person who does not know Newton's laws and have him/her view a bound state (one dimension for simplicity). The person observes a velocity $v = dx/dt$ which becomes zero at the endpoints and also sees time reversal symmetry. To account for time reversal symmetry, the person may suggest constructing an even function of $v(x)$. The simplest is:

$$v(x)v(x) \text{ (or } v \cdot v \text{) in three dimensions} \quad ((5))$$

Simply because ((5)) is the simplest even function does not imply it is the one which describes nature. We suggest, however, that it is for the following reason. Consider the highest value of $v(x)v(x)$ in the bound state and write:

$$v(x)v(x) + V_1(x) = E_1 \quad \text{where } E_1 = v_{\max} * v_{\max} \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is an a priori conservation law, but why can one not use other even functions of $v(x)$?

We introduce a second physical consideration, which also appears in Newtonian mechanics. A particle with rest mass m_0 has inertia. This means that it takes some effort to force it to move with a tiny dv . Double the mass seems to require double the effort. It seems one may measure this effort using dv/dx , but this must be multiplied by m_0 . Thus, one has:

Effort is proportional to $m_0 dv/dx$ ((7))

In such a case, one then sees that the form $v(x)v'(x)$ is appropriate, but that one should have:

$m_0 v(x)v'(x) + V(x) = E$ ((8)) if $m_0 dv/dx$ is to represent effort.

There is no need to have a factor of 2 appear with $m_0 dv/dx$, hence $1/2$ is introduced.

Thus, a priori, without any notion of momentum or Newtonian mechanics, one may introduce a conservation law to describe bound state motion. This is a local equation and one may make d/dx to obtain a differential equation:

$m_0 v dv/dx = -dV/dx$ Now $x = vt$ so $v dv/dt = -dV/dx$ or $m_0 v dv/dt = -dV/dx$ ((8))

To see that one may actually introduce Newtonian mechanics in an a priori manner, one may consider the alternative special relativistic approach.

Special Relativity

We again consider a person who is unaware of Newtonian mechanics, the concept of momentum or energy. This person sees a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t . A person in a moving frame (constant $-v$) sees a particle moving with speed v . If $x=0$, $t=0$ and $x'=0$, $t'=0$, i.e. the initial points coincide for both frames, then:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((9))$$

A person in a moving frame cannot have the same x',t' values as the person in the rest frame. ((9)) implies a transformation of (x,t) to (x',t') . If one introduces this as a matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ t' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} g(v) & -g(v)v/c \\ -g(v)v/c & g(v) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ t \end{bmatrix} \quad ((10))$$

If one considers a symmetric matrix, i.e.

$$\begin{bmatrix} g & -g v/c \\ -g v/c & g \end{bmatrix} \quad ((11))$$

then $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$, i.e. the speed of light is the same as viewed from different frames. This is consistent with the notion of a photon introduced by Maxwell from his electromagnetic equations.

Next, one may consider a conserved quantity (usually modulus) linked with ((11)). Normally, one would suggest:

$Xx + cctt$ ((12)), but if one considers:

$Xx, cctt$ and $gg(x+vt)(x+vt)$ and $gg(vx+t)(vx+t)$ with $x/t=c$, then:

$gg(xx+vvtt + 2xvt)$ and $gg(vvxx+tt + 2vxt)$

To remove the $2xvt$ term, one may suggest that a minus must appear, i.e.

$Xx - cctt = x'x' - cct't'$ leading to $g = 1/\sqrt{1 - vv/cc}$ ((13))

If one considers $x=0$, t , m_0 , with $c=1$,

$-tt = gg vvtt - gg tt$ ((14))

Multiplying by m_0 :

$-m_0 m_0 = (gm_0 v) (gm_0 v) - g m_0 m_0$ ((15))

$gm_0 v$ becomes $m_0 v$ in the $v/c \ll 1$ limit and

$m_0 \rightarrow m_0 + .5 m_0 v^2$ in the same limit. ((16))

The quantities which appeared in the previous section appear again and it seems one may use a priori arguments which contain hardly any dynamical physics, except for the $x/t = x'/t' = c$ condition, to see ideas of momentum and energy emerge. Thus, we suggest that the ideas of the previous section are not far -fetched.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that Newton's second law is sometimes obtained through a Lagrangian process, which is an extremely useful calculational approach. This approach makes use of variational calculus, i.e. different paths in spacetime are considered. As a mathematical procedure, this is fine, but there might be a tendency to consider that nature actually considers different paths in space. We argue that one may obtain Newton's second law from a strictly local approach based on an a priori conservation law, which may be written without knowing the concept of momentum or kinetic energy. This conservation law is local and leads to a local Newton's second law.